

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. P. L. Nayak, Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3, for many valuable suggestions and to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa for a research grant to support these investigations.

References

1. B. S. THYAGARAJAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, **58**, 439.
2. R. S. STEWART and W. A. BENJAMIN, *Oxidation Mechanism*, New York, 1964, p. 84.
3. C. D. COOK and R. C. WOOD WORTH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6242.
4. M. C. AGRAWALA and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1963, **72**, 1947.
5. I. R. WILSON, *Rev. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1966, **16**, 103.
6. V. N. SINGH, M. P. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 529.
7. P. T. SPEAKMAN and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955 **40**.
8. N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 557.
9. N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATAPATHY and P. L. NAYAK, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1973 **77A**, 163.
10. (a) N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 580.
(b) N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATAPATHY and P. L. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 770.
11. N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1973, **78A**, 57.
12. L. N. PATTANAIK, P. L. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 668.
13. N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
14. V. LAL, V. N. SINGH, N. S. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 329.
15. K. S. SUKLA, P. C. MATHUR and O. P. BANSAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1801.
16. C. A. COULSON, *Valence* (Oxford University Press, London), 1952.

Stability Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Ions Chelates of Schiff bases Derived from Sulphamethoxy pyridazine

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Manuscript received 25 September 1978, revised 23 March 1979, accepted 27 April 1979

IN continuation of studies¹ on the sulpha-drugs complexes, the present note embodies the stability constant of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) chelates of Schiff bases derived from sulphamethoxy pyridazine and salicylaldehyde (SMPSA) or *O*-hydroxyacetophenone (SMPHA) in 25% dioxane at 0.1M (NaClO₄) ionic strength at room

temperature (27±0.2°) using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti². The free energy change (ΔG° K cal mole⁻¹) and thermodynamic stabilisation energy (δH) are also calculated.

Experimental

The Schiff bases SMPSA and SMPHA were synthesised by condensing ethanolic solution of sulphamethoxy pyridazine and salicylaldehyde or *O*-hydroxyacetophenone in 1 : 1 ratio. The product obtained was crystallised from acetone.

All the metal ions solution were prepared from the corresponding sulphates, AnalaR (B.D.H.), in double distilled water. Sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid were standardized by usual methods. Chemically pure sodium perchlorate was used to keep the ionic strength constant.

Titration Procedure :

Potentiometric titrations were carried out as reported earlier³. The following mixtures (total volume 40 ml, ionic strength adjusted with 1.0M NaClO₄) keeping 25% (v/v) dioxane medium, were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (0.05M).

(A) 2.0 ml HClO₄ (0.05M), (B) A+10.0 ml Schiff base (0.01M), (C) B+2.5 ml metal ion solution (0.008M).

Results and Discussion

Formation functions $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated using the standard expressions⁴ from the titration curves A, B and C. The log $K_H^{\bar{n}}$ value of the ligands (pH at $\bar{n}_H=0.5$) was evaluated from the plots $\bar{n}_H$ versus pH . The formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ versus pL at different pH values. These plots indicate that the values of $\bar{n}$ obtained are of the order of two for all the metal ions under study, indicating the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (Metal : Ligand) complexes. Applying half integral method log K_1 and log K_2 were obtained and the values are reported in Table 1.

The order of stability constant of bivalent metal complexes with both the Schiff bases is as follows :

The order is in agreement with Irving and Williams order of stability of bivalent metal ions of 3d-series complexes⁴.

The difference between log K_1 and log K_2 (2.40±0.25) show the greater steric hindrance offered by the Schiff bases than coordinated water molecules as observed by Jain and Chaturvedi⁵.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANT, STABILITY CONSTANT, FREE ENERGY CHANGE (K Cal mole⁻¹) AND THERMODYNAMIC STABILISATION ENERGY OF THE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR COMPLEXES, AT 27°, $\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO₄) IN 25% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM

Cation	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁ /K ₂	-ΔG	δH
<i>Complexes with SMPSA</i>						
H(I)	6.45	—	—	—	8.87	—
Zn(II)	5.60	3.05	8.65	2.55	11.89	—
Cu(II)	5.75	3.40	9.15	2.35	12.58	24.94
Ni(II)	5.20	2.90	8.10	2.30	11.14	34.98
Co(II)	4.60	2.10	6.70	2.50	9.21	26.12
Mn(II)	3.75	1.50	5.25	2.25	7.22	—
<i>Complexes with SMPHA</i>						
H(I)	6.38	—	—	—	8.77	—
Zn(II)	5.50	3.00	8.50	2.50	11.69	—
Cu(II)	5.75	3.35	9.10	2.40	12.51	24.27
Ni(II)	5.15	2.80	7.95	2.35	10.93	34.28
Co(II)	4.50	2.05	6.55	2.45	9.00	26.23
Mn(II)	3.75	1.48	5.23	2.27	7.19	—

The standard-free energy change (ΔG K cal mole⁻¹) was calculated at 27° from the usual expression: $\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log \beta_2$ and is reported in Table 1.

The method described by George and McClure⁶ was used to calculate thermodynamic stabilisation energy (δH) for the metal ions under study from log K₁ of the SMPSA and SMPHA complexes. The Er (Mn–Zn) values found to be 49.54 and 49.40 respectively for SMPSA and SMPHA complexes are of the same order as observed for many other ligands which coordinate through one nitrogen atom. The δH value has been found to be 24.3 ± 0.04, 34.33 ± 0.05 and 26.17 ± 0.05 for Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes respectively under study. These values are of the same order for the ligand having coordination through oxygen and nitrogen atoms.

This fact is further supported by a slight shift to higher atomic number in the curve of ΔH_L (heat of complexation) against atomic number as compared to the curve of ΔH_H (heat of hydration of metal ion) against atomic number (Fig. 1). The straight lines joining Mn and Zn represent the situation in the absence of crystal field stabilisation.

Fig. 1. Values of ΔH_H (Curve A) and ΔH_L (Curve B) for Complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) relative to corresponding values for Mn(II).

Acknowledgement

Author is grateful to U. G. C., New Delhi, for financial assistance and M/s Cyanamide India Ltd., Bulsar, for supply of the pure sample of sulphamethoxy pyridazine.

References

1. K. LAL, *Acta Chim., Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1979, **99**, 281; *Acta Ciencia Ináica*, 1978, **4**, 242.
2. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; 1953, 3397.
3. K. LAL and S. P. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 260; *Rev. Chim. (Roumania)*, 1976, **27**, 657.
4. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
5. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 868.
6. P. GEORGE and D. S. McCLURE in "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", (Ed.), F. A. COTTON, Interscience, New York, 1959, Vol. 1, p. 428.